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**Impact Assessment of Car-Repair Activities on Non-Surface
Water Bodies in Ahoada East Local Government Area, Rivers State, Nigeria**

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Abstract

This study was an assessment into the impact of car-repair activities on the non-surface water (H₂O) bodies in Ahoada East Local Government Area, Rivers State Nigeria. It was carried out to assess the level of contamination and also the suitability of the non-surface H₂O for drinking. In all, three bore-holes stood analyzed for physico-chemical parameters; temperature, pH as well as electrical conductivity in addition to heavy metallic composition (lead (Pb), cadmium (Cd), iron (Fe), chromium (Cr), and zinc (Zn)). Non-surface H₂O samples were obtained from three functional boreholes within the car-repair vicinity with a control (non-surface H₂O) sample obtained far from the car-repair zone. All acquired data were compared with the World health Organization (WHO) recommended values for drinking H₂O quality. The latter showed that all assessed parameters remained within the acceptable limit set by the WHO apart from the pH whose value fall low indicating that the non-surface H₂O within the area remained somewhat acidic as the pH fluctuated from 6.0 to 6.5. Summarily, owing to the study it was concluded that the car-repair activities carried out in the area had not considerably affected the non-surface H₂O reserve. Though, the low pH specifies that the H₂O bodies involve slight treatment prior to human consumption. Periodic checking of the concentration of Fe within the non-surface H₂O reserve and other pollutants was the major recommendation.

Keywords: Impact assessment, car-repair, non-surface, water bodies.